

ANISOTROPIC LAMINATES THAT RESIST WARPING DURING MANUFACTURE

Dr P. M. Weaver

Dept of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol,
Queens Building, University Walk,
BS8 1TR, UK

SUMMARY: A variety of laminates have been identified that are asymmetric yet remain free from warping with changes in temperature. Rules for their identification have been established. These laminates contain various subsymmetries within them and may also exhibit coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane response. The least number of layers to obtain such a laminate is 8. A highly practical aspect of many of these laminates is their reliance on conventional fibre angles for lamination, i.e. 0° , 90° , 45° , -45° . Furthermore, their fabrication may make extensive use of non-crimped fabrics. To minimise warping curvatures it is recommended that laminates are designed using sublaminates based on $(0, 90, 90, 0)$ or $(45-45 -45 45)$.

KEYWORDS: Anisotropy, coupling, lay-up schemes, warping.

INTRODUCTION

Current design rules recommend use of balanced, symmetric laminates. Presumably, the former is suggested to eliminate in-plane anisotropic effects and the latter is partly suggested to eliminate warping in flat plates during hot-cure manufacture. However, it is noted that if these design rules are obeyed in curved structures then warpage remains. The wisdom of such overriding and limiting rules is currently being challenged. In this paper, a rationale is developed for laminate selection of unidirectionally multi-layered composite plates that identifies new rules for eliminating warping and suggests approaches for stacking sequence design in general. It builds upon the pioneering work of Bartholomew [1] who identified sets of laminates with orthotropic (specially orthotropic) properties. He discovered that there were many more non-symmetric, yet orthotropic, laminates than those that were symmetric—a feature that appears to have largely escaped the attention of composite design manuals. In particular, antisymmetric laminates in which the angle plies are grouped such that

$$(\theta, -\theta-\theta, \theta)_{as} \quad (1)$$

is obeyed gives the laminates with the least number of angle-ply layers that has orthotropic properties. It is a special lay-up and one which is practical for design because it is the optimal stacking sequence, with $\theta = 45^\circ$, for a flat plate subject to uniaxial compression loading in which buckling or natural frequencies are primary design drivers. It is also noted that this laminate is also orthotropic if $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $-\theta = 0^\circ$ or indeed vice-versa, despite the fact that the resulting laminate is not strictly antisymmetric. Bartholomew further adds that plies of 0° or 90° layers may be added to the outer layers and as long as these plies are

themselves symmetrically laminated about the resulting midplane then the laminate remains orthotropic. Examples of such laminates are

$$[90_n, 0_n, (\theta, -\theta - \theta, \theta)_{a/s}, 0_n, 90_n] \text{ and } [0_n, 90_n, (\theta, -\theta - \theta, \theta)_{a/s}, 90_n, 0_n] \quad (2)$$

where n has a minimal value of zero. Related work by Hajela and Erisman [2] also appear to have examined similar lay-ups. In contrast to Bartholomew, our interest is not specially orthotropic laminates but those laminates that do not warp when cooled from an elevated cure temperature. As such, materials of prime interest are the unidirectional reinforced prepreg materials such as those composite made from carbon, Kevlar or glass reinforced epoxies/phenolics and the like. First the conditions for laminates to remain flat are established and then a systematic study is undertaken to identify those laminates with **B** couplings that remain flat despite an elevated cure temperature. Finally, guidelines are given for aiding identification of lay-ups that lead to warp-free laminates.

DEVELOPMENT OF WARP-FREE CONDITIONS

Constitutive Behaviour

The constitutive expressions relating stress resultants, N_{ij} and M_{ij} to strains, ε_{ij} and curvatures, κ_{ij} for a thin laminate subject to thermal loads are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{N} &= \mathbf{A}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \mathbf{B}\boldsymbol{\kappa} - \Delta T \cdot \mathbf{N}^{th} \\ \mathbf{M} &= \mathbf{B}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\kappa} - \Delta T \cdot \mathbf{M}^{th} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} stiffness matrices are given in terms of the material invariants, U_1-U_5 and lamination parameters, $\xi_1-\xi_{12}$ (e.g. Fukunaga [3]) as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{12} \\ A_{22} \\ A_{66} \\ A_{16} \\ A_{26} \end{Bmatrix} &= t \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1 & \xi_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_1 & \xi_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{\xi_3}{2} & \xi_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\xi_3}{2} & -\xi_4 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} W_1 \\ W_2 \\ W_3 \\ W_4 \\ W_5 \end{Bmatrix} \\ \begin{Bmatrix} B_{11} \\ B_{12} \\ B_{22} \\ B_{66} \\ B_{16} \\ B_{26} \end{Bmatrix} &= \frac{t^2}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \xi_5 & \xi_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\xi_5 & \xi_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\xi_7}{2} & \xi_8 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\xi_7}{2} & -\xi_8 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} W_1 \\ W_2 \\ W_3 \\ W_4 \\ W_5 \end{Bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} D_{11} \\ D_{12} \\ D_{22} \\ D_{66} \\ D_{16} \\ D_{26} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{t^3}{12} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_9 & \xi_{10} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_{10} & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_9 & \xi_{10} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_{10} & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{\xi_{11}}{2} & \xi_{12} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\xi_{11}}{2} & -\xi_{12} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} W_1 \\ W_2 \\ W_3 \\ W_4 \\ W_5 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

and the thermal loads by[4]

$$\mathbf{N}^{th} = \begin{Bmatrix} N_x^{th} \\ N_y^{th} \\ N_{xy}^{th} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{t}{2} \begin{Bmatrix} W_1^{th} + W_2^{th} \xi_1 \\ W_1^{th} - W_2^{th} \xi_1 \\ W_2^{th} \xi_3 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{M}^{th} = \begin{Bmatrix} M_x^{th} \\ M_y^{th} \\ M_{xy}^{th} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{t^3}{8} \begin{Bmatrix} W_2^{th} \xi_5 \\ -W_2^{th} \xi_5 \\ W_2^{th} \xi_7 \end{Bmatrix}$$

Note that ΔT indicates temperature change. In this study it represents the temperature change from the matrix gel-point to room temperature.

The lamination parameters, ξ_i , may be calculated from the following integrals

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_1 \quad \xi_2 \quad \xi_3 \quad \xi_4) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (\cos 2\theta_i \quad \cos 4\theta_i \quad \sin 2\theta_i \quad \sin 4\theta_i) (u_i - u_{i-1}) \\ (\xi_5 \quad \xi_6 \quad \xi_7 \quad \xi_8) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (\cos 2\theta_i \quad \cos 4\theta_i \quad \sin 2\theta_i \quad \sin 4\theta_i) (u_i^2 - u_{i-1}^2) \\ (\xi_9 \quad \xi_{10} \quad \xi_{11} \quad \xi_{12}) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (\cos 2\theta_i \quad \cos 4\theta_i \quad \sin 2\theta_i \quad \sin 4\theta_i) (u_i^3 - u_{i-1}^3) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$u_i = \frac{2h_i}{t}$$

where h_i is the distance of the i^{th} ply from the mid plane, θ_i is its ply angle and t is the thickness of laminate with n plies. The material stiffness invariants, W_i , are linear functions of the ply stiffness properties, Q_{ij} ,

$$\begin{aligned} W_1 &= \frac{3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}}{8} \\ W_2 &= \frac{Q_{11} - Q_{22}}{2} \\ W_3 &= \frac{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}}{8} \\ W_4 &= \frac{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}}{8} \\ W_5 &= \frac{W_1 - W_4}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

as are the thermoelastic invariants, W_i^{th} ,

$$\begin{aligned}
W_1^{th} &= \alpha_{11}Q_{11} + (\alpha_{11} + \alpha_{22})Q_{12} + \alpha_{22}Q_{22} \\
W_2^{th} &= \alpha_{11}Q_{11} + (\alpha_{22} - \alpha_{11})Q_{12} - \alpha_{22}Q_{22}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

To gain some understanding of the physical nature of W_1^{th} and W_2^{th} it is noted that W_1^{th} simplifies to a Young's modulus multiplied by its thermal expansion coefficient for an isotropic material and that W_2^{th} vanishes. As such, the latter may be thought of as a measure of thermoelastic anisotropy whilst the former is a measure of thermoelastic isotropy of a composite material.

Warp-free conditions

To establish curing curvatures, it is necessary to set \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{M} to zero in Eqn. (3), substitute for $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and rearrange for $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
\boldsymbol{\kappa} &= \Delta T \cdot \mathbf{D}^{*-1} (\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{N}^{th} - \mathbf{M}^{th}) \\
\text{with } \mathbf{D}^* &= \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where \mathbf{D}^* is the reduced stiffness matrix. Note warping curvatures, $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$, depend on in-plane, \mathbf{N}^{th} as well as out-of-plane thermal loads, \mathbf{M}^{th} . This may be understood by identifying $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{-1}$ as an ‘‘eccentricity’’ or ‘‘moment arm’’ matrix, which is a matrix measure of the distance from midplane to a notional neutral plane. For zero warping, $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = 0$, such that

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{N}^{th} = \mathbf{M}^{th} \tag{10}$$

Eqn. (10) represents 3 equations that must be satisfied for a laminate to resist thermal warping. Note, they are not dependent on flexural stiffnesses, \mathbf{D} and are therefore a function of only 8 lamination parameters. Despite this simplification, it is difficult to obtain a simple analytical solution in terms of these 8 lamination parameters that satisfies Eqn. (10). In fact, the mixed nature of thermoelastic invariants (i.e. the combination of elastic and thermal properties) in \mathbf{N}^{th} and \mathbf{M}^{th} contrasting with the relatively simple nature of stiffnesses invariants, W_i renders a general solution involving integer ply angles unlikely. To obtain solutions, we will use some physical insight. Actually, there are many solutions. These may be classified according to various symmetries and subsymmetries in the laminate. For instance, one obvious solution to Eqn. (10) is

$$\mathbf{N}^{th} = \mathbf{M}^{th} = 0 \tag{11}$$

However, on close examination of Eqn. (5) it is realised that it is impossible to simultaneously eliminate both N_x^{th} and N_y^{th} . Therefore the conditions of Eqn. (11) are never realised. However,

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{M}^{th} = 0 \tag{12}$$

is a solution, noting that ensuring $\mathbf{B} = 0$ automatically satisfies $\mathbf{M}^{th} = 0$. Examples of such orthotropic composites are, of course, those that are symmetrically laminated. In addition to these are the suite of orthotropic yet nonsymmetric laminates demonstrated by Bartholomew [1], examples of which are shown in Eqns. (1) and (2). From Eqn. (5) it is seen that to obtain $\mathbf{M}^{th} = 0$ requires

$$\xi_5 = \xi_7 = 0 \tag{13}$$

or

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \cos 2\theta_i = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \sin 2\theta_i = 0 \quad (14)$$

where

$$p_i = u_{i+1}^2 - u_i^2 = 2i - 1 - n \quad (15)$$

The term p_i is a weighting factor on either $\cos 2\theta_i$ or $\sin 2\theta_i$. Each successive term contributes to an arithmetic progression that advances by 2 for every successive term.

It is noted that a non-symmetric laminate must have more than one distinct ply angle otherwise the laminate is symmetric. If two distinct ply angles are used then it is possible to solve both expressions in Eqn.(14) for θ to give

$$P_a = P_b = 0 \quad (16)$$

or

$$\theta_b = \theta_a + 90$$

where

$$P_a = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^a; P_b = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^b; \quad (17)$$

and p_i^a and p_i^b refer to positions of two different ply orientations a and b , respectively. Furthermore, it is noted that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 0; \quad (18)$$

for an even or odd number of uniformly thick plies. Note, also that if $P_a = 0$ then according to Eqn. (16), $P_b = 0$ for a laminate with 2 distinct ply orientations. For example, the $(0, 90)_s$ laminate has values of $p_1^{90} = 0, p_2^{90} = -1, p_3^{90} = 1$ and $p_4^{90} = 0$ and $p_1^0 = -3, p_2^0 = 0, p_3^0 = 0$ and $p_4^0 = 3$. Although symmetric laminates such as this satisfy the conditions in Eqn. (16), symmetry is not necessary. The least number of layers to achieve this in a nonsymmetric laminate is 7 and is

$$(\theta_a, \theta_b, \theta_b X, \theta_a, \theta_a, \theta_b) \quad (19)$$

where X represents an arbitrary ply angle. For a laminate with an even number of layers the least number of layers is 8 and is described by

$$(\theta_a, \theta_b, \theta_b \theta_a)_{a/s} \quad (20)$$

and both examples satisfy the first sufficient condition in Eqn.(16). It is noted that these non-orthotropic laminates are generalisations of the orthotropic laminates proposed by Bartholomew [1] of which, that shown in Eqn. (1) is an example. If the second criterion in Eqn.(16) is satisfied then

$$P_b = -P_a \frac{\cos 2\theta_a}{\cos 2\theta_b} = -P_a \frac{\cos 2\theta_a}{\cos 2(\theta_a + 90)} = P_a$$

and is only satisfied when the first condition in Eqn.(16) is satisfied., i.e. there is only one solution for Eqn. (14) where 2 distinct ply orientations are concerned. There are other sub-solutions though. It is noted that if we denote the sum of p_i for a particular fibre orientation on one half of the mid-plane by P_{a+} (above midplane) and P_{a-} (below midplane) we can establish further criteria that guide in selection of such laminates. First note that the sum of p_i for half the laminate (i.e. on one side of the midplane) is given by

$$P_{a-} + P_{b-} = \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} p_i = -\frac{n^2}{4}; P_{a+} + P_{b+} = \sum_{i=n/2+1}^n p_i = \frac{n^2}{4} \text{ for even number of layers} \quad (21)$$

$$P_{a-} + P_{b-} = \sum_{i=1}^{(n-1)/2} p_i = \frac{1-n^2}{4}; P_{a+} + P_{b+} = \sum_{i=(n+1)/2}^n p_i = \frac{n^2-1}{4} \text{ for odd number of layers}$$

and that

$$P_{a+} + P_{a-} = P_a = 0$$

$$P_{b+} + P_{b-} = P_b = 0 \quad (22)$$

Currently the non-symmetric laminates with $\mathbf{B} = 0$ that have so far been identified in Eqns. (19) and (20) are characterised by

$$P_{a+} = P_{b+}$$

$$P_{a-} = P_{b-} \quad (23)$$

and are *cross-symmetric*, meaning for every position with ply angle, θ_a above midplane there is a ply angle, θ_b at the same position below the midplane. With increasing number of plies there are an increasing number of solutions that satisfy Eqn. (23). Table 1 shows such laminates based on 2 distinct ply orientations. Laminates, with up to 13 basic plies have been included, noting that laminates with more plies are readily found using conditions of Eqns. (21) and (22). Note that X, Y, Z and Q indicate an arbitrary ply orientation and can take values of θ_a, θ_b or indeed, any angle. Furthermore, X, Y, Z and Q are not limited to single ply angles. Each may also represent a sublaminates which itself may be symmetrical or nonsymmetrical; noting that for cases where each sublaminates is not symmetrical then its ply order is reversed on the other side of the laminate midplane. For example, consider laminate 7 in Table 1 where $X = (0 \ 90)$ then the overall laminate is

$$(\theta_a, \theta_b, \theta_b, 0, 90, 90, 0, \theta_a, \theta_a, \theta_b) \quad (24)$$

It is noted that there is a combinatorial increase in the number of such laminates with increase in ply angle and that the basic laminate numbers 7 and 9 repeat many times as basic elements in laminates with larger number of plies. As such these basic laminates are called *parent* laminates and the derived laminates are *children*. These relationships are shown more clearly in Fig. 1. The basic repeating pattern in Laminate number 7 is $\theta_a, \theta_b, \theta_b$ and in laminate no 8 it is $\theta_a, \theta_b, \theta_b, \theta_a$ and are termed sublaminates. They share a common trait, i.e. $P = 0$ for them. For Laminate number 7 the plies occupy positions 2, 3 and 4 and in laminate number 8 they occupy positions 1, 2, 3 and 4, noting it is only necessary to consider one half of the laminate. If one of the basic repeating sequences has been split in a child laminate it is represented by an 'S' (split) on the branches in Fig. 1. It is surprising how few parent laminates there are. Others include 10d (children 12h and 13q); 11h (child 13k); 12i; 12j; 13n; 13r and 13s. Further features may be gleaned from the laminates in Table 1 and 2. All laminates comprise *spliced* sublaminates. Consider the overall laminate where sublaminates may be identified that have been split and added together.

Table 1: Non-symmetric laminates with $B = 0$ (up to 13 plies)

Laminate	No of plies	Lay-up (Nonsymmetry and $B = 0$)	P_a^+	P_b^+	P_{X-Q}^+
7	7	$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	6	6	0
8	8	$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	8	8	0
9a	9	$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	10	10	0
9b		$\theta_a \theta_b Y \theta_b X \theta_a Y \theta_a \theta_b$	8	8	4
9c		$Y \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Y$	6	6	8
10a	10	$X \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b X$	8	8	9
10b		$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a X X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	12	12	1
10c		$\theta_a \theta_b X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_a \theta_b$	10	10	5
10d		$\theta_a X \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_a X \theta_b$	9	9	7
11a	11	$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a Y X Y \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	14	14	2
11b		$Y \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Y$	10	10	10
11c		$\theta_a \theta_b Y \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_a Y \theta_a \theta_b$	12	12	6
11d		$Z Y \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Y Z$	6	6	18
11e		$Z \theta_a \theta_b Y \theta_b X \theta_a Y \theta_a \theta_b Z$	8	8	14
11f		$\theta_a \theta_b Z Y \theta_b X \theta_a Y Z \theta_a \theta_b$	10	10	10
11g		$\theta_a Z \theta_b \theta_b Y X Y \theta_a \theta_a Z \theta_b$	10	10	10
11h		$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b Y X Y \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b$	10	18	2
12a	12	$Y \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a X X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Y$	12	12	12
12b		$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a Y X X Y \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	16	16	4
12c		$\theta_a \theta_b Y \theta_b \theta_a X X \theta_b \theta_a Y \theta_a \theta_b$	14	14	8
12d		$Y X \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b X Y$	8	8	20
12e		$Y \theta_a \theta_b X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_a \theta_b Y$	10	10	16
12f		$\theta_a \theta_b Y X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a X Y \theta_a \theta_b$	12	12	12
12g		$\theta_a Y \theta_b \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_a Y \theta_b$	12	12	12
12h		$Y \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a X \theta_b Y$	9	9	18
12i		$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b$	18	18	0
12j		$\theta_a Y \theta_b X \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_a Y \theta_b$	11	11	14
13a	13	$Z \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a Y X Y \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Z$	14	14	14
13b		$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a Z Y X Y Z \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	18	18	6
13c		$Z Y \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Y Z$	10	10	22
13d		$Z \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a Y X Y \theta_b \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Z$	14	14	14
13e		$Z \theta_a \theta_b Y \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_a Y \theta_a \theta_b Z$	12	12	18
13f		$\theta_a \theta_b Z \theta_b \theta_a Y X Y \theta_b \theta_a Z \theta_a \theta_b$	16	16	10
13g		$Q Z Y \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b Y Z Q$	6	6	30
13h		$Q Z \theta_a \theta_b Y \theta_b X \theta_a Y \theta_a \theta_b Z Q$	8	8	26
13i		$Q \theta_a \theta_b Z Y \theta_b X \theta_a Y Z \theta_a \theta_b Q$	10	10	22
13j		$Q \theta_a Z \theta_b \theta_b Y X Y \theta_a \theta_a Z \theta_b Q$	10	10	22
13k		$Q \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b Y X Y \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b Q$	10	18	14
13m		$\theta_a Z \theta_b \theta_b Y \theta_a X \theta_b Y \theta_a \theta_a Z \theta_b$	14	14	14
13n		$\theta_a \theta_b Z Y \theta_b \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_a Y Z \theta_a \theta_b$	14	14	14
13o		$\theta_a Y \theta_b \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a Y \theta_b$	16	16	10
13p		$\theta_a Q \theta_b Z \theta_b Y X Y \theta_a Z \theta_a Q \theta_b$	12	12	18
13q		$\theta_a \theta_b Q Z Y \theta_b X \theta_a Y Z Q \theta_a \theta_b$	12	12	18
13r		$\theta_a Z Y \theta_b \theta_b \theta_b X \theta_a \theta_a \theta_a Y Z \theta_b$	12	12	18
13s		$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_b Y \theta_a \theta_a X \theta_b \theta_b Y \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b$	18	18	6
13t		$\theta_a \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b \theta_b Y X Y \theta_a \theta_a \theta_b \theta_a \theta_b$	20	20	2

The sublaminates, based on θ_a and θ_b are nearly all cross-symmetrically laminated in the overall laminate. Yet, the sublaminates based on X , Y , Z and Q are symmetrically laminated in the overall laminate.

Fig 1: Parent / Child classification scheme for nonsymmetry with $B = 0$ (up to 13 layers)

The laminate in Eqn. (24) shows these features. The cross-symmetry of the sublaminates based on θ_a and θ_b is shown in Table 1 by the fact that $P_a^+ = P_b^+$. Only one parent laminate was found (up to 13 layers) that does not have elements of cross-symmetry, it is 11h. Table 2 shows how $P_a^+ \neq P_b^+$ for 11h

Table 2 Calculation of P_a and P_b for Laminate number 11h

ply	θ_a	θ_b	θ_b	θ_b	Y	X	Y	θ_a	θ_a	θ_b	θ_b
Position	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
p_i	-10	-8	-6	-4	-2	0	2	4	6	8	10

(Numbers in **bold** type represent p_i for θ_a .)

In fact, $P_a^+ = 10 = -P_a^-$ and $P_b^+ = 18 = -P_b^-$

For the cross-symmetric laminates in which X , Y , Z and Q are sublaminates based on θ_a and θ_b then the following sums are obeyed,

$$P_a = P_b = \frac{n^2}{8} \text{ for even number of layers} \quad (25)$$

$$P_a = P_b = \frac{n^2 - 1}{8} \text{ for odd number of layers}$$

and where P_a and P_b must be even in magnitude.

Coupled Laminates $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$

Up until now we have considered laminates that have $\mathbf{B} = 0$, noting that this requirement automatically satisfies $\mathbf{M}^{th} = 0$, and therefore Eqn. (10) for thermally warp-free laminates. Yet, it is also possible to satisfy Eqn. (10) with nonorthotropic laminates such that $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$. One such solution is

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{N}^{th} = \mathbf{M}^{th} = 0 \quad (26)$$

noting, once again, that is impossible to simultaneously eliminate N_x^{th} and N_y^{th} . On close examination of Eqn. (5) and (4) it is a necessary requirement that $\xi_5 = \xi_7 = 0$ to obtain $\mathbf{M}^{th} = 0$ yet ξ_6 and ξ_8 have no such constraints. Therefore, from Eqn. (4) a possible solution involves

$$B_{11} = B_{22} = \xi_6 W_3 = -B_{12} = -B_{66} \quad (27)$$

The problem of solving the 3 equations in Eqn. (6) is still complicated by the fact there are 6 remaining lamination parameters. The next simplification involves eliminating N_{xy}^{th} . Once again, the motivation for doing this is to minimise the solution's dependence on thermoelastic invariants, W_i^{th} . From Eqn. (5) this happens when $\xi_3 = 0$. It is noted that all cross-ply laminates, i.e. those laminates based on 0° and 90° plies satisfy $\xi_3 = 0$. This is not a necessary requirement, however, as all balanced laminates (i.e. those laminates that contain equal number of θ_a and $-\theta_a$ plies) satisfy this condition also. A subset of balanced laminates that also satisfies this condition are the laminates with equal numbers of evenly orientated ply angles (i.e. ply angles given by $360/n, 2*360/n, 3*360/n \dots (n-1)*360/360, 360$ where n is an integer ≥ 3). Substituting $\xi_3 = 0$ and conditions of Eqn. (27) into the first 2 equations in Eqn. (26) gives

$$\begin{aligned} a_{11}N_x^{th} - a_{22}N_y^{th} - a_{12}(N_x^{th} - N_y^{th}) &= 0 \\ -a_{11}N_x^{th} + a_{22}N_y^{th} + a_{12}(N_x^{th} - N_y^{th}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

and these equations are identical to each other. Here a_{ij} denotes in-plane compliance terms given by $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}$. In general, the only solution to this occurs when

$$N_x^{th} = N_y^{th} \quad (29)$$

The combination of thermal expansions and stiffness properties in the thermoelastic invariants W_i^{th} that comprise \mathbf{N}^{th} in comparison with the stiffness only invariants, W_i of \mathbf{a} renders other solutions unlikely. Furthermore, if $N_x^{th} = N_y^{th}$ then according to Eqn. (29)

$$a_{11} = a_{22} \quad (30)$$

must hold. Then Eqn. (29) gives

$$\xi_1 = 0 \text{ and } A_{11} = A_{22} \quad (31)$$

In summary, to find thermally stable laminates with $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$, it is generally necessary to ensure

1. $\mathbf{M}^{th} = 0$ giving $\xi_5 = \xi_7 = 0$
2. $N_{xy}^{th} = 0$ giving $\xi_3 = 0$
3. $N_x^{th} = N_y^{th}$ giving $\xi_1 = 0$

An exhaustive search of the feasible region of the 12 lamination parameters failed to find solutions that did not obey the above 3 conditions and confirms the difficulty of finding general solutions when mixed invariant terms are present, i.e. W_i^{th} and W_i . Having established the 3 conditions that must be satisfied it remains to find laminate solutions. Condition 3 also gives $A_{11} = A_{22}$. This is only met if the laminate is balanced about an angle 45° or -45° to the x - and y -directions. This concept is explained in Fig.2 where 2 ply angles are shown that are at angles of $+\theta$ to the 45° and -45° axes.

Fig. 2: One possible lay-up to obtain $\xi_3 = 0$

Therefore to satisfy $\xi_3 = 0$, the simplest sublaminates must comprise the following angles

$$, 45+\theta, -45+\theta \quad (32)$$

To satisfy $\xi_5 = \xi_7 = 0$ then the ply order does matter. First all, expanding ξ_5 gives

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_5 &= p_1 \cos 2(45+\theta) + p_2 \cos 2(-45+\theta) & \xi_7 &= p_1 \sin 2(45+\theta) + p_2 \sin 2(-45+\theta) \\ &= (p_1 - p_2) \sin 2\theta & &= (p_1 - p_2) \cos 2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

noting that the ply order is currently arbitrary. To satisfy these conditions more plies more must be added. To ensure this requirement we may use the sublaminates scheme featured in laminate 8 i.e. $\theta_a, \theta_b, \theta_b, \theta_a$ and arrange the plies as

$$45+\theta, -45+\theta, -45+\theta, 45+\theta \quad (34)$$

where $P_{45+\theta} = P_{-45+\theta} = 8$. To obtain a final solution we may add additional sublaminates in which θ is different for each sublaminates to obtain

$$([45+\theta_a, -45+\theta_a, -45+\theta_a, 45+\theta_a], [45+\theta_b, -45+\theta_b, -45+\theta_b, 45+\theta_b], [45+\theta_c, -45+\theta_c, -45+\theta_c, 45+\theta_c]) \quad (35)$$

where 3 sublaminates have been shown, each for different θ . There is no limit to the number of sublaminates based on Eqn. (34) or indeed the order to which they are arranged. Consider the case where 2 sublaminates have been arranged one with $\theta_a = 45$ and the other based on $\theta_a = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} &0, 90, 90, 0, 45, -45, -45, 45 & (36) \\ \text{or} &90, 0, 0, 90, 60, -30, -30, 60 \end{aligned}$$

Note that the laminates in Eqn. (36) have non-zero \mathbf{B} terms such that $B_{11} = B_{22} = -B_{12} = -B_{66}$ as anticipated in Eqn. (27), yet remain warp-free with changes in temperature. It is noted that such laminates may be readily made using non-crimped fabrics. Furthermore, making laminates from sublaminates based on that given in Eqn. (34) will minimise warping curvatures upon curing.

It is also possible to identify other sublaminates by combining others in various permutations. For instance, instead of adding sublaminates we may evenly splice them together, e.g.

$$\mathbf{0}, 45, \mathbf{90}, -45, \mathbf{90}, -45, \mathbf{0}, 45 \quad (37)$$

where the sublaminates in Eqn. (34) have been spliced together. To emphasise this the first sublaminate has been shown in bold. This laminate may have practical application since it shows in-plane elastic isotropy and the angle between layers is 45° as opposed to the 90° shown in Eqn. (35), which may have benefits with regards to minimising interlaminar stresses. A key feature, using these ply orientations, is to ensure that the 0° and 90° plies are evenly spaced to retain the relative position of the 0° and 90° plies within the parent sublaminate $0, 90, 90, 0$ or $0, 90, 90, 0$. Using these guidelines two further examples are

$$\mathbf{0} \mathbf{90} 45-45 \mathbf{90} \mathbf{0} -45 45 \text{ and } \mathbf{90} 45 -45 \mathbf{0} -45 45 \mathbf{0} -45 45 \mathbf{90} 45 -45 \quad (38)$$

Of course, many permutations are possible. Sublaminates other those based on that shown in Eqn. (34) are possible, e.g. $(\theta, 60+\theta, -60+\theta)$ [2]. Another point to note is that all the laminates with $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$ that remain thermally warp-free are thermally isotropic [2] such that $\alpha_{xx} = \alpha_{yy}$.

All laminates identified here are conventionally described as asymmetric but that description fails to convey the high degree of sub-symmetries contained within the stacking sequence. A more appropriate descriptor for such laminates is *subsymmetrical* - the *sub* indicates groups of sublaminates within the laminate that contain various types of symmetry within the sublaminate. Examples include those shown above that have sublaminates that are themselves symmetrically or antisymmetrically laminated. Furthermore, if such a laminate has orthotropic properties it is appropriate to describe it as a subsymmetrical orthotropic laminate.

CONCLUSIONS

The conditions for establishing thermally warp-free laminates have been found. Many nonsymmetric laminates have been identified that exhibit no coupling between in- and out-of-plane response $\mathbf{B} = 0$, yet may retain A_{i6} or D_{i6} anisotropies. As such, these laminates are a generalisation of the nonsymmetric orthotropic laminates shown by Bartholomew [1]. Furthermore, many more laminates have been shown that exhibit coupling response $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$ yet remain thermally warp-free. All laminates contain a mixture of sublaminates that are themselves cross-symmetric or symmetric. Such laminates have been described as subsymmetrical in nature

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank Dr Cezar Diaconu for his help with exhaustive lamination parameter studies and Albert Pérez Subirós and Sergio Narro Millán for pursuing undergraduate studies on this topic.

REFERENCES

1. Bartholomew, P., *Laminate Stacking Sequences for Special Orthotropy*, ESDU data sheet no. 82013, Engineering Sciences Data Unit, London, 1982
2. Hajela, P. and Erisman, In Chapter 3 and Chapter 5 of *Design and Optimization of Laminated Composite Materials* by Gurdal, Z. , Haftka, R. T. and Hajela, P. Wiley, 1999
3. Fukunaga, H. “Stiffness Optimisation of Orthotropic Laminated Composites using Lamination Parameters”, *AIAA Journal* 29(4), 1991, pp641-646
4. Diaconu, C. Z. and Sekine, H. “Erratum on Flexural Characteristics and Layup Optimization of Laminated Composite Plates using Lamination Parameters”, *J. of Thermal Stresses*, Vol 27, 2004, pp1213-1216